

Viscosities of binary and ternary liquid mixtures of alkylbenzenes with carbon tetrachloride in cyclohexane

Bharati Bhattacharjee^a and S. N. Bhat^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, St. Mary's College, Shillong-793 003, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 003, India

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The viscosities of ternary mixtures of benzene-carbon tetrachloride, toluene-carbon tetrachloride and *o*-xylene-carbon tetrachloride in cyclohexane have been determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. The data are analyzed using Frankel model. Viscometric data are used to study the interaction between the weakly interacting systems. The equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters are reported.

There has been an increasing interest in the study of interaction between weakly interacting systems, and a number of experimental techniques have been used to investigate the interaction between electron donors and electron acceptors with or without a third component¹. Even though spectroscopic techniques are the most powerful tools to investigate such interactions, these methods are subject to criticism as the separation of equilibrium constant *K* and the extinction coefficient ϵ from $K\epsilon$ becomes increasingly difficult with the decrease in the strength of interaction². It is surprising that although the knowledge of viscosity of multicomponent liquid mixtures is of particular interest in chemical industry, there is hardly any report on the viscosities of ternary systems³. It was, therefore, felt worthwhile to have reliable experimental data for suitable ternary systems which are scarce and then use the data to study the molecular interaction between electron donors with electron acceptors in suitable media, viscometrically. The systems chosen for such purposes are : benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene (as electron donors), carbon tetrachloride (as electron acceptor) and cyclohexane (as solvent).

Results and Discussion

The viscosities of benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and car-

bon tetrachloride in cyclohexane were determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K and the values are summarised in Tables 1–4. The viscosities of benzene, toluene and *o*-xylene in cyclohexane decrease with increase in concentration of benzene whereas those of carbon tetrachloride in cyclohexane increase with the increase in concentration of carbon tetrachloride. Here it may be mentioned that benzene and alkyl benzenes are electron donors whereas carbon tetrachloride is an electron acceptor. Therefore, the interaction between benzene and cyclohexane is of different nature compared to that between carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane. The excess viscosity η^E which is given by

$$\eta^E = \eta_{\text{obs}} - (\eta_1 x_1 + \eta_2 x_2) \quad (1)$$

where η_1 , η_2 and x_1 and x_2 are viscosities and mole fractions of the components 1 and 2 respectively, is proportional to the concentration of the 'associated species'. Each of the mixtures were fitted to a smooth equation,

$$\eta^E = x(1 - x) \sum A_j (1 - 2x)^j \quad (2)$$

where x is the mole fraction of benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and carbon tetrachloride and A_j are the fitting parameters, the values of which are given in the respective tables. The excess viscosity varies in the order : benzene-cyclohexane

Table 1. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for binary system of benzene-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Mole fraction of benzene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
0.1	8.0394	7.4789	0.5605	7.3236	6.8250	0.4986	6.7226	6.2912	0.4314	6.2240	5.8890	0.3350
0.2	7.8110	6.8998	0.9112	7.1279	6.3626	0.7653	6.5563	5.8240	0.7323	6.0891	5.5045	0.5850
0.3	7.5826	6.5130	1.0696	6.9322	5.9993	0.9329	6.3900	5.5330	0.8670	5.9545	5.2320	0.7230
0.4	7.3541	6.1939	1.1603	6.7365	5.7327	1.0037	6.2237	5.3231	0.9006	5.8199	5.0220	0.7979
0.5	7.1257	5.9435	1.1822	6.5410	5.5036	1.0374	6.0574	5.1465	0.9109	5.6853	4.8620	0.8230
0.6	6.8973	5.8710	1.0263	6.3450	5.4332	0.9118	5.8911	5.0753	0.8158	5.5506	4.7860	0.7646
0.7	6.6689	5.7621	0.9068	6.1493	5.3417	0.8076	5.7248	4.9838	0.7410	5.4160	4.7474	0.6686
0.8	6.4405	5.7507	0.6898	5.9536	5.3634	0.5902	5.5585	5.0020	0.5565	5.2814	4.7279	0.5535
0.9	6.2121	5.8198	0.3923	5.7579	5.4088	0.3491	5.3922	5.0241	0.3680	5.1467	4.7646	0.3821

Table 2. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for binary system of toluene-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Mole fraction of toluene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
	0.1	7.9981	7.4115	0.5866	7.2867	6.7761	0.5106	6.6887	6.2129	0.4758	6.1888	5.7780
0.2	7.7284	6.8106	0.9178	7.0540	6.2312	0.8227	6.4883	5.7777	0.7106	6.0192	5.4279	0.5913
0.3	7.4587	6.3384	1.1204	6.8214	5.8652	0.9562	6.2879	5.4705	0.8175	5.8496	5.1667	0.6829
0.4	7.1891	6.0309	1.1581	6.5887	5.6155	0.9732	6.0876	5.2585	0.8291	5.6800	4.9770	0.7030
0.5	6.9194	5.8444	1.0750	6.3561	5.4309	0.9251	5.8873	5.1118	0.7755	5.5104	4.8466	0.6638
0.6	6.6497	5.7457	0.9040	6.1234	5.3313	0.7921	5.6869	5.0142	0.6727	5.3408	4.7485	0.5923
0.7	6.3800	5.6079	0.7720	5.8908	5.2309	0.6599	5.4866	4.9496	0.5370	5.1712	4.7040	0.4672
0.8	6.1103	5.5454	0.5650	5.6581	5.2190	0.4391	5.2862	4.9004	0.3858	5.0016	4.6700	0.3316
0.9	5.8407	5.3077	0.5330	5.4255	5.1910	0.2345	5.0860	4.8897	0.1962	4.8320	4.6721	0.1599

Table 3. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for binary system of *o*-xylene-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Mole fraction of <i>o</i> -xylene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
	0.1	8.1559	7.6911	0.4648	7.4306	7.0027	0.4279	6.8125	6.4158	0.3967	6.3025	5.9794
0.2	8.0441	7.3090	0.7351	7.3418	6.6947	0.6471	6.7360	0.1714	0.5646	6.2466	5.7578	0.4887
0.3	7.9322	7.0598	0.8724	7.2531	6.4879	0.7652	6.6596	5.9927	0.6670	6.1906	5.6212	0.5694
0.4	7.8204	6.9115	0.9090	7.1644	6.3765	0.7879	6.5831	5.8980	0.6850	6.1347	5.5410	0.5937
0.5	7.7085	6.8373	0.8712	7.0757	6.3374	0.7383	6.5066	5.8571	0.6496	6.0788	5.5644	0.5144
0.6	7.5966	6.8280	0.7686	6.9869	6.3038	0.6832	6.4302	5.8383	0.5920	6.0229	5.5618	0.4610
0.7	7.4848	6.8040	0.6810	6.8982	6.3317	0.5666	6.3537	5.8987	0.4550	5.9669	5.6018	0.3651
0.8	7.3729	6.7910	0.5821	6.8095	6.4068	0.4027	6.2772	5.9484	0.3288	5.9110	5.6487	0.2623
0.9	7.2610	6.6750	0.3860	6.7208	6.4992	0.2216	6.2007	6.0181	0.1827	5.8551	5.7134	0.1417

Table 4. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for binary system of CCl₄-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Mole fraction of CCl ₄	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
	0.1	8.3940	8.1764	0.2176	7.6567	7.4653	0.1914	7.0148	6.9618	0.0530	6.4901	6.4651
0.2	8.5203	8.1890	0.3313	7.7941	7.5120	0.2821	7.1340	7.0196	0.1145	6.6218	6.5478	0.0740
0.3	8.6465	8.2386	0.4079	7.9314	7.5945	0.3369	7.2564	7.0296	0.2268	6.7536	6.5703	0.1833
0.4	8.7728	8.2720	0.5008	8.0688	7.6920	0.3768	7.3925	7.0543	0.3382	6.8853	6.6234	0.2620
0.5	8.8991	8.3778	0.5213	8.2062	7.7826	0.4236	7.5185	7.1341	0.3844	7.0170	6.7080	0.3089
0.6	9.0253	8.5583	0.4671	8.3435	7.9710	0.3725	7.6444	7.3287	0.3157	7.1487	6.8850	0.2637
0.7	9.1516	8.7031	0.4485	8.4809	8.1299	0.3510	7.7703	7.5510	0.2193	7.2804	7.1174	0.1630
0.8	9.2779	9.0140	0.2640	8.6183	8.3552	0.2631	7.8962	7.7450	0.1512	7.4121	7.3562	0.0559
0.9	9.4041	9.2791	0.1250	8.7557	8.6528	0.1029	8.0221	7.9471	0.0750	7.5438	7.5150	0.0288

> toluene-cyclohexane > *o*-xylene-cyclohexane, indicating that the strength of interaction depends on the shape (steric effects) of the molecules in addition to the polarizability. As the observed values of viscosity differ from the calculated values (assuming ideal mixtures) various relations, namely, Kendle and Munroe's relation⁴, additive relation which is combination of Arrhenius model⁵, Eyring model⁶, Hind's relation⁷ and Frankel model⁸ were tried and it was found that one can use the model proposed by Frankel for such non-ideal binary/ternary systems. For binary systems, the equation that can be used is

$$\ln \eta = x_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + x_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + 2 x_1 x_2 \ln \eta_{12} \quad (3)$$

where η_{12} is a constant. This equation when extended to ternary liquid mixtures takes the form,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \eta = & x_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + x_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + 2 x_1 x_2 \ln \eta_{12} + \\ & x_3^2 \ln \eta_3 + x_2 x_3 \ln \eta_{23} + x_3 x_1 \ln \eta_{31} + \\ & 3(x_1 x_2 x_3 \ln \eta_{123}) \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where η is the observed viscosity of two mixed systems, η_1 , η_2 , η_3 are the viscosities, and x_1 , x_2 , x_3 are the mole fractions of the components 1, 2, and 3 respectively. The viscosities of the binary systems at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are given in the Tables 2–5. From the present data of binary mixtures it is evident that there is interaction between cyclohexane and benzene, and between cyclohexane and carbon tetrachloride. The maximum deviation in the plot of η^E against the mole fraction of benzene in benzene-cyclohexane appears at ≈ 0.5 mole fraction, indicating the presence of 1 : 1 complexes.

Table 5a. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for ternary system of benzene-CCl₄-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Total concn = 1 mole

Molar concn. of benzene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
0.0	8.4031	8.1792	0.2239	7.6665	7.4475	0.2190	7.0239	6.8290	0.1948	6.4996	6.3519	0.1474
0.1	8.3649	8.0636	0.3013	7.6307	7.3808	0.2499	6.9925	6.7468	0.2460	6.4710	6.2919	0.1791
0.2	8.3271	7.9970	0.3301	7.5951	7.3217	0.2734	6.6912	6.6888	0.2720	6.4424	6.2550	0.1873
0.3	8.2892	7.9304	0.3588	7.5596	7.2603	0.2993	6.9227	6.6377	0.2850	6.4139	6.1903	0.2236
0.4	8.2514	7.8469	0.4045	7.5240	7.2033	0.3207	6.8990	6.5989	0.3000	6.3855	6.1380	0.2475
0.5	8.2137	7.7620	0.4520	7.4866	7.1425	0.3461	6.8680	6.5297	0.3380	6.3571	6.0728	0.2843
0.6	8.1756	7.6921	0.4835	7.4527	7.0777	0.3750	6.8363	6.4890	0.3470	6.3285	6.0188	0.3097
0.7	8.1313	7.6114	0.5199	7.4117	7.0203	0.3914	6.8005	6.4308	0.3697	6.2963	5.9820	0.3143
0.8	8.0924	7.5614	0.5310	7.3752	6.9588	0.4164	6.7685	6.3804	0.3880	6.2672	5.9339	0.3333
0.9	8.0538	7.5110	0.5430	7.3390	6.8960	0.4429	6.7368	6.3238	0.4130	6.2405	5.8820	0.3585
1.0	8.0249	7.4491	0.5758	7.3112	6.8495	0.4017	6.7121	6.2836	0.4286	6.2152	5.8433	0.3718

Table 5b. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for ternary system of benzene-CCl₄-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Total concn = 2 moles

Molar concn. of benzene	298.15K			303.15K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
0.0	8.5353	8.1830	0.3523	7.8104	7.4796	0.3308	7.1558	6.8596	0.2962	6.6375	6.4152	0.2223
0.2	8.4599	7.9865	0.4735	7.7395	7.3418	0.3977	7.0936	6.7510	0.3430	6.5808	6.3139	0.2668
0.4	8.3847	7.8462	0.5385	7.6688	7.2320	0.4368	7.0311	6.6530	0.3780	6.5242	6.2063	0.3178
0.6	8.3102	7.7048	0.6054	7.5988	7.1162	0.4826	6.9700	6.5266	0.4435	6.4681	6.1099	0.3582
0.8	8.2352	7.5617	0.6735	7.5283	6.9868	0.5415	6.9082	6.4266	0.4816	6.4115	6.0168	0.3947
1.0	8.1604	7.4430	0.7174	7.4580	6.8966	0.5614	6.8465	6.3250	0.5215	6.3553	5.9185	0.4368
1.2	8.0860	7.3423	0.7437	7.3882	6.7683	0.6199	6.7853	6.2205	0.5649	6.2995	5.8250	0.4745
1.4	8.0118	7.2340	0.7778	7.3184	6.6520	0.6664	6.7250	6.1167	0.6083	6.2435	5.7444	0.4991
1.6	7.9381	7.1161	0.8220	7.2491	6.5440	0.7051	6.6640	6.0188	0.6450	6.2241	5.6693	0.5550
1.8	7.8645	6.9939	0.8706	7.1798	6.4340	0.7458	6.6025	5.9161	0.6854	6.1330	5.5366	0.5964
2.0	7.7910	6.8695	0.9215	7.1108	6.3325	0.7783	6.5149	5.8261	0.7158	6.0774	5.4745	0.6029

Table 6. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for ternary system of toluene-CCl₄-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Total concn = 1 mole

Molar concn. of toluene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
0.0	8.4031	8.1792	0.2239	7.6665	7.4475	0.2190	7.0239	6.8290	0.1948	6.4996	6.3519	0.1476
0.1	8.3610	8.0761	0.2850	7.6269	7.3565	0.2705	6.9891	6.7445	0.2446	6.4674	6.2737	0.1936
0.2	8.3180	7.9900	0.3190	7.5872	7.2801	0.3070	6.9541	6.6798	0.2743	6.4350	6.2082	0.2267
0.3	8.2758	7.9276	0.3469	7.5476	7.2020	0.3456	6.9191	6.6020	0.3170	6.4027	6.1551	0.2457
0.4	8.2333	7.8499	0.3834	7.5079	7.1260	0.3819	6.8844	6.5350	0.3491	6.3708	6.0895	0.2812
0.5	8.1906	7.7636	0.4269	7.4680	7.0505	0.4175	6.8489	6.4599	0.3889	6.3380	6.0227	0.3153
0.6	8.1478	7.6781	0.4697	7.4297	6.9896	0.4401	6.8136	6.4060	0.4076	6.3055	5.9719	0.3337
0.7	8.1051	7.5981	0.5070	7.3881	6.9144	0.4740	6.7785	6.3313	0.4471	6.2730	5.9178	0.3551
0.8	8.0620	7.5527	0.5092	7.3482	6.8577	0.4950	6.7431	6.2797	0.4633	6.2403	5.8540	0.3866
0.9	8.0190	7.4799	0.5390	7.3080	6.7807	0.5273	6.7076	6.2075	0.5001	6.2076	5.7878	0.4198
1.0	7.9760	7.4253	0.5507	7.2675	6.7050	0.5625	6.6721	6.1407	0.5313	6.1748	5.7404	0.4344

The excess viscosity values $\eta^E = (\eta_{obs} - \eta_{cal})$, which are negative over the entire range of composition, indicate that probably dispersion forces (non-specific interaction) rather than the molecular rearrangement between dissimilar molecules⁸ play an important role in such systems and the relative deviation should be an indication of the strength of such interaction between the molecules⁹. From the present data it is clear that the strength of non-specific interaction between cyclohexane and alkylbenzenes varies in the order, benzene-cyclohexane > toluene-cyclohexane > o-

xylene-cyclohexane (Fig. 1), indicating that the strength of interaction depends on the shape (steric effect) of the molecule in addition to polarizability. The trend is maintained at all the temperatures at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. This trend is in good agreement with the observations made by Nigam *et al.*¹⁰ for aromatic hydrocarbons-nitromethanes.

The viscosities of ternary systems, namely, alkylbenzenes-carbon tetrachloride-cyclohexane of different compositions were determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and

Table 7. Experimental and calculated values of viscosity (mPaS) for ternary system of *o*-xylene-CCl₄-cyclohexane at various temperatures

Total concn. = 1 mole

Molar concn. of <i>o</i> -xylene	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
	η_{calc}	η_{exptd}	η^E									
0.0	8.4031	8.1792	0.2239	7.6665	7.4475	0.2190	7.0239	6.8290	0.1948	6.4996	6.3519	0.1476
0.1	8.3780	8.1163	0.2617	7.6425	7.3897	0.2528	7.0050	6.7602	0.2444	6.4800	6.2884	0.1916
0.2	8.3524	8.0561	0.2963	7.6185	7.3396	0.2790	6.9807	6.7161	0.2650	6.4598	6.2438	0.2160
0.3	8.3273	7.9947	0.3326	7.5950	7.2969	0.2980	6.9594	6.6766	0.2827	6.4398	6.2132	0.2265
0.4	8.3013	7.9441	0.3572	7.5717	7.2403	0.3314	6.9376	6.6253	0.3123	6.4196	6.1777	0.2418
0.5	8.2754	7.8874	0.3880	7.5457	7.2009	0.3447	6.9246	6.5910	0.3336	6.3995	6.1348	0.2650
0.6	8.2498	7.8375	0.4122	7.5212	7.1256	0.3956	6.9025	6.5385	0.3640	6.3789	6.0978	0.2811
0.7	8.1972	7.7881	0.4355	7.4965	7.0992	0.3973	6.8807	6.4999	0.3808	6.3588	6.0513	0.3074
0.8	8.1972	7.7440	0.4532	7.4714	7.0629	0.4085	6.8582	6.4651	0.3931	6.3382	6.0163	0.3219
0.9	8.1717	7.6774	0.4943	7.4472	7.0351	0.4121	6.8366	6.4269	0.4097	6.3180	5.9867	0.3313
1.0	8.1450	7.6329	0.5121	7.4219	6.9999	0.4220	6.8051	6.3746	0.4305	6.2970	5.9552	0.3418

313.15 K. No maxima/minima were found in the viscosity curves but the nonlinear plot of excess of viscosity vs concentration of alkyl benzenes indicates the existence of interaction between the molecules (Tables 5–7). From the continuous variation plot of η^E , the difference in viscosity between the calculated and observed values for the ternary systems (keeping the solvent mole fraction constant and varying the amount of interacting species), the stoichiometry of benzene-carbon tetrachloride systems in

Fig. 1. Variation of η^E , the difference between η_{cal} and η_{obs} with the mole fraction of alkyl benzenes at 298.15 K : (1) benzene-cyclohexane, (2) toluene-cyclohexane and (3) *o*-xylene-cyclohexane.

cyclohexane in the experimental range of concentration was found to be $\approx 1 : 1$. On the basis of calorimetric measurements, similar observations were made earlier¹¹. The deviation in η^E values decreased with the increase in temperatures and they are reversible. The equilibrium constants and the free energies of formation of complexes obtained from the above mentioned procedure are summarised in Table 8, and it is evident that the equilibrium constants obtained from viscometric measurements are slightly different from the literature data obtained by

spectroscopic method. Here it can be recalled that Kohler¹² had rightly pointed out that the thermodynamic properties of liquid mixtures are frequently influenced by association or complexation equilibria between certain molecular species. It is difficult to compare the equilibrium constants and the other (derived) thermodynamic properties obtained by spectroscopic methods with those obtained by non-spectral methods, as the former deals with concentration whereas the latter with activities of the species i.e. for comparison the concentrations should be comparable. Christian and Lane¹³ showed the importance of activity coefficient corrections enter in different ways when different physical methods are used to study the same complex equilibria. The limitations of various methods used in determining the equilibrium constants were reported by Foster¹⁴. Prue¹⁵ argued that even purely contact charge-transfer complex can give rise to equilibrium constant of the order of K_c 0.31 mol⁻¹ and it is difficult to accept the lower values (e.g. 0.21 for benzene-CCl₄) reported in the literature. Moreover, while comparing the data/results one must see that the experimental conditions are the same. So we feel that in such weakly interacting systems, one must look into the relative values rather than the absolute values. The equilibrium constant (K_c) decreases from benzene-carbon tetrachloride to *o*-xylene-carbon tetrachloride. The trend in the present investigation goes in parallel with the literature data trend (reported from calorimetric studies). The decrease in K_c values with the inclusion of CH₃ group in benzene indicates that in molecular interactions the size and shape of the molecules (i.e. geometry) are probably more predominating (at least in viscometric studies) compared to the polarizability (as the shape of the molecules determines the 'closeness' of the partners). The heat of formation of these 'adducts' are slightly higher; the free energies are positive ($k < 1$) and entropies are small and positive. The negative ΔS° values show that the complex is in more ordered form compared to the free components. From the present results it is evident that the viscosity measurements can be used to detect the 'interaction' between the molecules. As it stands, the present viscometric procedure demands very careful

Table 8. Equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters of alkyl benzenes-CCl₄ in cyclohexane

Systems	$K_c^* M^{-1}$				$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹ at 298.15 K	$-\Delta S^\circ$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ at 289.15 K
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K			
Benzene-CCl ₄	0.34 (0.215)	0.29	0.26	0.23	20.6	2.66	0.078
Toluene-CCl ₄	0.27 (0.413)	0.25	0.23	0.22	11.0	3.27	0.048
<i>o</i> -Xylene-CCl ₄	0.25	0.23	0.22	0.21	9.7	3.39	0.044

* K_c values were calculated from the K_x values by using the equation, $K_x = K_c 1000 d_s/M_s$, where K_x and K_c are the equilibrium constants in mole fraction and concentration units, d_s = density of the solvent in g. ml⁻¹, M_s the molecular wt. of the solvent, error limits for K_c , $-\Delta H^\circ$, $-\Delta G^\circ$ and $-\Delta S^\circ$ are ± 0.01 , ± 1.5 , ± 0.06 , ± 0.001 respectively.

Values in parenthesis refer to the literature data [*J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 673].

measurement of viscosity involving long flow time to realise significant difference between solvent and dilute solutions. In addition, there are experimental difficulties, such as accurate measurements of flow times, large amount of solutions, precise temperature control, dust and grease free materials etc. Moreover, the measurements are time-consuming. However the method is useful where no alternative is available.

Experimental

Cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene and *o*-xylene (B.D.H.) were purified by standard procedures¹⁰. The density and boiling point of the liquid are presented in Table 9.

Table 9

Solvent	B.p. °C	Density $\times 10^3$ kg m ⁻³	Viscosity mPas
Cyclohexane	79 (80–82)	0.77632 (0.7785)	8.2678 (8.28)
Carbon tetrachloride	75 (76)	1.58906 (1.5844)	9.5304 (9.09)
Benzene	79 (80)	0.87541 (0.8790)	5.984 (6.028)
Toluene	108 (110)	0.86231 (0.8623)	5.571 (5.516)
<i>o</i> -Xylene	142 (143)	0.87630	7.1492

Values in parenthesis refer to the literature values (Refs. 16, 17).

The density and viscosity of pure samples and their binary and ternary mixtures were determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 (± 0.01) K using a vibrating densitometer DMA 48 fitted with a Haake G thermostat and an Ubbelohde viscometer. The experiments were repeated at least twice and the results were reproducible with the experimental error of 0.00002 kg m⁻³ and 0.0002 mPaS respectively. The stoichiometries of the 'associated' species were determined by Jobs¹⁸ continuous variation method.

The non-linear plot of any physical property of mixed solution against the concentration of the components, i.e. the deviation from ideal behaviour of the pure components in solution (after correcting the values for the solvent contribution) is an indication of the interaction between the two species, e.g. between a donor D, and an acceptor A. If one can assume that the deviation is entirely due to the as-

sociated species alone, then the deviation should be proportional to the concentration of the associated species. Therefore, it was felt that equilibrium constant (K) for the association can be calculated by following the procedure of Yoshida and Osawa¹⁹ which is of general nature.

For equimolar mixture of D and A (with total concentration C), the maximum deviation RS , in any of the physical properties, here η , from the additivity, can be written as

$$RS = \alpha x \quad (5)$$

where α is a proportionality constant and x is concentration of the complex. When the total concentration is changed from C to C' , then

$$R'S' = \alpha x' \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } RS/R'S' = \alpha x/\alpha x' = k \quad (7)$$

In the present case, K_x is given by

$$K_x = x/[(C/2)-x]^2 = x'/[(C'/2)-x']^2 \quad (8)$$

Combining (7) and (8) and rearranging, we obtain,

$$K_x = 2\sqrt{k} \{ \sqrt{k(C+C')-(C+kC')} \} / (C-kC')^2 \quad (9)$$

As the plot of η^E vs concentration is not always symmetrical, k is actually the ratio of the areas under the curves.

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